

Article

Human Trafficking: the Dark side of Humanity

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DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.8285413

Abstract

The present paper examines the human trafficking as a growing problem in the contemporary world. It highlights the factors, indicators, stages and stigma associated with human trafficking. It also includes the preventive measures to combat this social menace.

Key Words: Human Trafficking, Traffickers, Stigma, Protection, Prosecution, Prevention, Stakeholders

Introduction

Human trafficking has become an issue of international as well as a national significance since the last few decades. Different studies conducted in various countries have shown that thousands of women and girls are being trafficked across borders and within countries. Even though, the trafficking has transformed into a global issue, lack of systematic research leads to unavailability of reliable data that would allow comparative analyses. Men,

women and children cutting across the boundary of nations are becoming the victims of human trafficking. It is now a well accepted supposition that women and the children are the major victims of trafficking. According to UNIFEM (2004), two million children are trafficked globally every year and unfortunately almost half of them, under the age of seven, are compelled to work in the flesh trade.

Human trafficking is considered as a multi-dimensional social phenomenon that is plaguing all the nation states of the present world. Sometimes the term 'trafficking' also leads to confusion as it includes multiple issues like forced labor, slavery, prostitution and many other things. According to United Nations (2000) human trafficking is: "..... the recruitment, transportation, transfer, harboring or receipts of persons, by means of threat or use of force or other forms of coercion, of abduction, of fraud, of deception, of abuse of power or of a position of vulnerability or of giving or receiving payments or benefits to achieve the consent of a person having control over another person for the purposes of exploitation. Exploitation shall include, at a minimum, the exploitation or the prostitution of others or other forms of sexual exploitation, forced labour or services, slavery or practices similar to slavery, servitude or removal of organs".

According to SAARC Convention on Preventing and Combating Trafficking in Women and Children for Prostitution,(2002), 'trafficking means moving, selling or buying women and children for prostitution within and outside a country for monetary or other considerations with or without the consent of the person subjected to trafficking.

Article 23 of the Constitution of India prohibits trafficking in human beings for any type of

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exploitation, including forced labour and any contravention is a punishable offence.

The offence of trafficking has been defined in the Section-5 of the Immoral Traffic (Prevention) Act, 1956. It indicates that trafficking includes procuring, taking and/ or inducing a person for the sake of prostitution. According to this section, even an attempt to procure and take or cause a person to carry on prostitution amounts to trafficking. Therefore 'trafficking' has been given a broad scope and meaning under ITPA.

Trafficking of human beings is not a recent phenomenon as it can be traced back in the pages of history. It was part of Global slavery and slavery is an issue that cannot be safely consigned to the past as it continues to exist even in the contemporary world and can be found even in the developed countries like France and the United States (Bales,1999).

Factors behind Trafficking

There are several push and pull factors which are responsible for human trafficking. The report "Trafficking in Women and Children, Child marriage and dowry: a study for action plan in West Bengal" Compiled by Prof .Ghosh) states the following factors for trafficking. They are as follows:

- I. Poverty coupled with frequent, almost annual, floods leading to virtual destitution of some people
- II. Lack of employment opportunities
- III. Low status of the girl child
- IV. Lack of literacy and awareness amongst girls
- V. Low rates of prosecution of traffickers

- VI. A weak law enforcement machinery
- VII. Trafficking as a lucrative trade
- VIII. Increasing demand of young girls for sexual exploitation

According to a study by Clert et al (2005) - the main individual risk factors for becoming a victim of transnational human trafficking are age, gender, being a member of a minority group and having a low level of education. The study shows that unemployment, alone, is not necessarily the driving force. Rather, it is the false promise of a better economic opportunity that is the root cause of luring victims of human trafficking. Regarding household risk factors, Clert et al(2005) find that poverty is an important factor, especially for child victims of human trafficking.

The social, economic and political causes are extremely complex. It is argued that women are marginalized from the job market and from education. Sexual exploitation of women and children is prevalent in many cultures where men continue to enjoy more power than women and children. Some countries have a strong economic stake in the success and perpetuation of human trafficking. This is particularly true for tiny countries whose gross national product depends on sex tourism (Ferguson, 2003).

Political instability also plays a role in human trafficking. Political conflicts have helped the traffickers across the globe. When the law and order of a nation state breaks down, the women and children become vulnerable. It is true that political instability does not directly lead to trafficking but it allows perpetrators to target vulnerable group and most of the times, women and children fall prey to them.

Migration is another factor that needs to be looked at. It is strongly predicted that as migration increases, so will the number of people being trafficked (Survivor's Right International, Kempadoo, 2005). In fact, the international office of migration estimates that 150 million people migrate each year in search of better economic opportunities, or to escape gender discrimination, armed conflict, political instability and poverty (Survivor's Right International) and of these, two million will become trafficked victims (Survivor's Right International; McGill, 2003). Traffickers transport nearly four million illegal migrants each year, revealing just how closely migration is interlinked with that of trafficking (Renzetti et al, 2001).

Poverty also negatively contributes the trafficking phenomenon. Kevin Bales asserts that "..... it is poverty that makes people vulnerable to being enslaved in present times" (Bales, 2005). Currently, most of the Latin American Countries and African Countries have more than 40 percent of the population living below poverty line (CIA World Factbook, 2005). Poverty forces the women of the developing world to adopt different methods of survival for themselves and their families. The lack of employment or little opportunities for employment often forces women to travel beyond their homes to acquire economic security and freedom. The movement is not free from risk and it is often seen that they fall in the hands of traffickers.

Corruption is the one of the major factors in fostering global human trafficking. Corruption occurs at various points- during the documentation, exploitation, border crossing, and transportation. By convening with traffickers, governmental officials, police, customs, and immigration services, law

enforcement officials, security forces, and domestic agents, corruption repeatedly allows the movement of victims between countries (Bales, 2005). Without corruption, human trafficking would not be as extensive as it is today (Malarek, 2004).

Human deception is a common method that is applied to trick people into trafficking trap.

False employment advertisements, promises of marriage, etc play a vital role in the trafficking trade. Once individuals are taken into custody by traffickers, their personal documents are taken into custody by traffickers, and they are no longer free and it should be noted that this form of deception is not limited to the females but also occurs with males.

Hennink and Simkhada (2004) in their study found out that there are four routes of trafficking- through brokers, independent migration to urban areas, deception and false marriage, and by force/ abduction. Based on this study, trafficking is commonly conducted by familiar people including uncles, cousin brothers, and step fathers and so on.

The study conducted by UNIFEM (2004) has categorized the main causes of trafficking into two groups- root causes and immediate causes. The immediate causes are seen in the form of illiteracy, family's dysfunctionality and all forms of discrimination including violence, forced marriage and divorce. Similarly, the root causes are determined as gender discrimination, poverty, unemployment, impact of globalization, discriminatory cultural values and religious beliefs and practices.

In addition to the above, UNIFEM (2004) have placed the abovementioned causes into two dimensions, i.e. push and pull factors.

The push factors include the immediate and root causes and it exists at the origin. On the other hand pull factor is seen as a result of the international phenomena, including the international migration policies, demand for cheap labour market and domestic workers, the booming sex industry, increasing use of children as entertainers, and globalization.

In India, men's patriarchal perception, attitude and beliefs towards the children and women have also been recognized as the contributing factors facilitating both the supply of and demand for trafficking. In fact the women and children are thought of as commodities that could be sold and resold in the markets (UNIFEM, 2004).

Indicators of Human Trafficking

Indicators are of utmost importance in understanding the dimensions, extent and ramifications of human trafficking (Nair, 2010). It is also considered important to measure the harm done to the victim as well as the gains to the exploiter. Knowledge of indicators is relevant and offered a help to those who are engaged in the war against human trafficking.

The indicators of the process of trafficking can be broadly listed as generic and specific (Nair,2010). The generic indicators are as follows:

- I. Commercial exploitation of a person where the exploiter, who could be one or more persons located at different places, gain monetarily out of the exploitation of the person
- II. There is an economic activity with money transaction to the benefit of one or more persons

- III. The ambience around the trafficked person is exploitative and involve several crimes and violations
- IV. Huge assets accrue to the exploiter from continuous exploitation of victim/victims
- V. The exploiter would have established adequate safety valves, protective measures and chain of command to ward off any onslaught by the law agencies or media
- VI. Nexus of the exploiters with other exploiters and even responders is another generic indicator. The nexus may appear to be one of friendship but could be deep rooted and conspiratorial

The specific Indicators of the process of human trafficking are as follows-

- I. There is an element of displacement of the trafficked person from the original community to the exploited community. This, more often, involves transportation from the source area to the destination area (Nair,2010)
- II. There is a presupposition that trafficked person is a victim
- III. The trafficked person is considered as vulnerable. The vulnerability factor exists because of the number of reasons like lack of awareness of rights, lack or inadequate education, weak support system, loss of parents, conflicts in the society, natural calamities etc
- IV. Weak redressal mechanisms for the victims and vulnerable persons
- V. Demand for sex in hotels, massage parlours and in places of sex tourism is a clear indicator that trafficking of girls

and boys for sexual exploitation does take place in these places.

The Human Trafficking Population

It is estimated that 600,000 to 800,000 innocent lives are stolen each year (Bales, 1999). Approximately 70 percent of these victims are female and 50 percent are children (U.S. Department of State, 2005). Of the approximate 4 million people who are trafficked around the world each year, over one million are trafficked into the sex industry (Gerdes, 2006). The International Organization of Migration (IOM) estimates that between 700,000 and 2 million women are trafficked across international borders yearly (Gerdes, 2006). One non-governmental organization, Survivor's Rights International (2006) estimates that 1 to 2 million people are trafficked around the world each year.

Profit Generated By Human Trafficking Worldwide

Human trafficking generates huge illegal profit in the world. Renzetti et al (2001) estimated that profit range from \$5 billion to \$7 billion. The United Nations Office on Drugs and Crime estimates that worldwide, the trafficking industry yields \$7 billion annually. Current estimate report that the trafficking in human beings is worth \$30 to \$40 billion (Rosenthal, 2007). It has become a "multi-billion dollar industry". The victims are either engaged in forced labour or sexual exploitation (United Press International, 2007).

The Stages of Human Trafficking

Human trafficking is an organized crime and it follows certain stages.

Stage-I- The victim is either abducted or recruited under false promises. The deception of part of the traffickers plays a vital role.

Stage-II- The victim faces exploitation. The traffickers either force them to do labour or provide sexual services.

Lastly, the traffickers may find it necessary to launder criminal offences as well, such as smuggling of weapons or drugs" (Bales, 2005).

According to Kevin Bales (2005), there are eight stages involve in trafficking. The stages are as follows- the context of vulnerability, recruitment, removal, transportation, establishment of control, arrival, exploitation and resolution.

Crimes related to Human Trafficking

Bales (2005) has also identified the associated crimes so far human trafficking is concerned. These crimes can be summed up as follows-

- I. Recruitment of Victim- Document forgery, Fraudulent promises, kidnapping
- II. Transportation of victim- Document forgery, Immigration law abuse, corruption of officials, damage to property, withholding of documents
- III. Exploitation of the victim- Unlawful coercion, threat, extortion, false imprisonment, kidnapping, procurement, theft of documents, sexual assault, Rape, Murder, Forced Abortion.
- IV. Disposition of criminal proceeds- money laundering, tax evasion, corruption of officials

Existence of Human Trafficking

Human trafficking exists everywhere and no country is free from this menace. Trafficking may occur internally or internationally (Barry, 1995). There are certain countries which serve as the source or the origin states, there are few which act as the transit states and there are countries which are known as the destination states. Transit countries usually serve as midway points where traffickers make false document, visas etc. Destination countries usually include developed or developing economies with flourishing sex trade like Japan, USA, the Netherlands, Thailand, Germany, Taiwan, South Korea, and India (Renzetti et al, 2001). Origin countries are mainly poor and developing countries and include much of the Africa, Latin America, Central and Eastern Europe and Southeast Asia. According to Survivor's Rights International (2005), approximately 100,000 women and children are trafficked very year across Latin America and the Caribbean. The organization also found that after crackdown in Asia on sex tourism, trade in the Americas has increased at an alarming rate.

It is pertinent to look into the scenario in and around India. The country is surrounded by Bangladesh, Pakistan, Nepal and Sri Lanka. India is considered a source country, transit country as well as destination state so far human trafficking is concerned. Now country wise discussion would give a vivid picture of the trafficking menace.

Bangladesh

Trafficking is no new phenomenon in this country. It all started probably in the year 1975 when a group initiated human trafficking as an organized activity. It has increased since 1985. According to UNICEF and SAARC report, every month 120 to 150 Bangladeshi women are trafficked to Pakistan. Bangladesh National

Women Lawyers' Association stated that traffickers use few common methods like promise of a job abroad with a handsome salary, fake marriage or child marriage, polygamy etc. (Source: Jonaki, 1997)

Pakistan

Pakistan plays an important role in the field of trafficking of women and children as a receiving, transit and as well as a destination country. Though it is an open secret that a lot of women and children are trafficked to Middle East countries for nefarious purposes but no reliable data is available (Source: Jonaki, 1997).

Sri Lanka

Sri Lanka is an island nation and there are no land borders. So traffickers are bound to adopt the sea route or air route. It is comparatively difficult and it helps to prevent large scale trafficking in the state. However, within the country from the rural areas to the cities, the women and children are trafficked by organized groups and agents within the country (Source: Jonaki, 1997).

Nepal

Trafficking of Young girls and women in Nepal is not a recent phenomenon. According to Sangroula (2001), trafficking of Nepalese girls and women to the red light areas of Indian cities became established by 1960s. It increased in the following two decades. According UNIFEM (2008), disparity in the economic status and gender inequality are responsible for trafficking in Nepal. Although it is difficult to identify the accurate number of Nepalese girl trafficking, the International Labour Organization (2001) estimates that approximately 12,000 Nepalese children are trafficked to Indian brothels and the

Gulf countries every year for the purpose of commercial sex work.

Moreover, many recent studies show that the number of trafficking to sex industry is increasing as the women are being trafficked to new destinations Asia, Europe and The U.S.A (Terre des Home, 2003).

In case of India , data provided by the National Crime Records Bureau show there were 7,647 cases of women being trafficked in 1984 and the figure increased to 11,242 in 2002 (Ghosh and Kar,2006). The situation has further gone downward. It can be seen from the NCRB report that the reported cases of trafficking have touched 4,541 in the year 2006 (NCRB Report, 2010).The situation in West Bengal is even worse than the national scenario. The State Police have declared that over 2,500 teenaged girls have disappeared from Bengal in the year 2009 (Source: The Telegraph, 2010). A total 679 cases of trafficking of minor girls were reported in Bengal in the year 2010, as compared to 237 such cases in 2009, representing a 186.5% increase over 2009. An increasing trend was observed in such cases over the previous three years as well (Source: The Statesman, 2012).

Social Stigma associated with Human Trafficking

Oxford Dictionary of Sociology defines stigma as follows-although the term has a long history, it entered sociology mainly through the work of Erving Goffman. Goffman(1963) states that an individual possessing the bodily attributes such as cut as or burnt marks is avoided in public places. It is said that stigma is understood as an undesirable attribute that an individual possess reducing his/her moral status in society. As a stigma, stigma leads to social

exclusion, violence and discrimination. Goffman categorized three types of stigma which reduce the life chances of the stigmatized. Understanding the stigma is important as the trafficked victims and the rescued one face stigma in the society and it has an adverse impact on the reintegration process.

Goffman(1963) has also pointed out a range of strategies that the stigmatized people adopt to their situation. The coping strategies include avoidance, denial, positive framing, acceptance, emotional support, active coping and search for social support. It is important to look upon the stigma as the trafficked victims face it in the society and it also affects the self identity of the victims.

Preventing and Combating Human Trafficking

Different strategies have been adopted by different countries to address this menace. The basic response is awareness of human trafficking. Research has shown that ignorance about the dimensions of human trafficking has led many to think and believe that all trafficked women are 'Prostitutes' (Nair, 2010). Lack of response is a causal effect of lack of awareness. Interestingly, lack of awareness inevitably leads to lack of response or improper response. Awareness is the sine-quo-non of the response systems. Where there is total lack of awareness, response is hopeless or not existing at all.

Once the person is aware that human trafficking takes place, the response agencies need to understand the dimensions, the complexities involved in the offense, the violations that have taken place. This is the stage of convincing oneself and empowering oneself. The stage of cognizance has a very important role because even after awareness,

the response may not take place or may be inadequate unless and until the awareness factor translates itself into cognizance factor (Nair, 2010).

Inertia plays a stumbling block in addressing the issue of human trafficking. Even after the rising awareness level regarding human trafficking, it is taking place. This is because one fails to appreciate the gravity of the situation. This inertia is the result of several factors, especially prejudices, predilections, bias and predispositions which are ingrained within a person (Nair, 2010). This is further exacerbated by external issues like lack of cooperation between the law enforcement agencies and the public.

Research in the past has shown that that human trafficking either gets lowest priority or nil priority. Priorities are determined by the mindset of the responder himself, the attitude of the survivors, peers or court of laws, the media publicity etc. Lack of questioning of the trafficked victim also leads to the less priority by law enforcement agencies.

Lack of sensitivity is a major reason for branding the victims as offenders under the banner of soliciting persons (Nair,2010).

Trafficking is blatant violations of the basic human rights of human beings and the law enforcing agencies are often accused of ignoring the cases of human trafficking cases. Lack of concern can be witnessed in the administration.

One of the reasons for the lack of cognizance is inappropriate style of manpower utilization. The fact is that response to human trafficking cannot and should not wait. This should be considered as the extreme violation of the human rights and requires prompt

response. It has to be given top priority and manpower has to be augmented.

Lack of resource is often cited as one of the reasons for improper cognizance to human trafficking issues. The resource crunch, especially at the police stations is major constituent in denying or depriving or retarding the cognizance stage in the response pattern.

It is also to be noticed that some law enforcement officials have had a tough time with either the public, with bosses, media or with any other person or agencies while discharging duties. This harassment made him feel that it is better to withdraw or not to respond to such situations.

Human trafficking is an organized crime and it needs to be addressed from an organized crime perspective. But this is not known to many and because of this there is lack of proper cognizance.

Response

A crucial factor is the timely action. It helps reduce the risk to the victims. Quick delivery of justice can sooth the ruffled feathers. Delayed response is as harmful to the victims as lack of response. Human trafficking is a continuing offence and timely response at the earliest point of time is cardinal. Timely response brings honour to the responder and improves public trust and respect.

Identification of the victims is fundamental to response. It is needed to prevent as well as combat the menace. It helps to prevent the trafficking of the vulnerable person from being trafficked. Identification also helps post- rescue care and attention. It also

facilitates the policy formulation regarding anti-trafficking. Identification contributes to the reorientation and revision of the legal systems and brings the role of victims into the centrality of the entire anti- human trafficking process (Nair,2010).

Rescue is also a step so far response is considered. It is generally termed as a welfare activity but it is indeed a human rights act. The agencies are duty bound to rescue any person who is a victim or likely to be a victim. Even a person below eighteen years of age, vulnerable to trafficking is a child in need of care and protection and has to be rescued (The Juvenile Justice (care and protection of children) Act, 2000). Under Section -5 of The Immoral Traffic (Prevention) Act, 1956, attempt to trafficking is also a cognizable offence. Therefore, even before trafficking has been completed and even while an attempt is being made by the recruiter, the victim should be rescued. Therefore, in order to prevent violations and harm to the person, rescue assumes a pivoted role in the mandate of the response agencies (Nair, 2010).

Restoration and repatriation are responses which deal with the return of the rescued person to the original place of residence or to the proper ambience where the rescued person will be safe and sound. Restoration speaks about such transfer within the country and repatriation speaks about transfer across the border. NGOs may be involved in both processes.

Welfare measures include the humanitarian activities including relief, which may be in cash or kind. The rescued person needs change of clothes, medicines, food, a roof over head etc. Many government agencies provide certain amount of interim relief. Welfare measures

provide a temporary relief but it has a tremendous impact on the rescued victims.

Capacity building measures are those which provide the desired relief to the trafficked victims. The measures have long term impact and ultimately empower the trafficked victims. Counselling sessions by trained counselors is considered to be an essential step at this stage. The victim may be non-cooperative and sometimes violent but the counseling sessions are going to have an impact on them. So, it is necessary that the counselors should be well trained to handle the situation.

Economic empowerment is another important stage in capacity building. It begins when the victim is ready and willing to receive training on livelihood options. However the decision relating to the training is to be taken only after the victim is properly counseled and he/she has realized the importance of such training to become self independent and self reliant. While formulating capacity building process, following thing should be taken into account. They are as follows- willingness and the orientation of the victim, scope of the job in the market, sustainability of the job, scope for income generation, and scope for marketing of the products, scope for the financial assistance and above all the comfort level of the victim to accept job and continue it (Nair, 2010).

Reinforcing Measures is considered as the third stage of the protective measures. Once the victim is trained and provided with livelihood skills, there is need to revisit and see whether things are moving in the right direction. NGOs can be actively engaged in monitoring activities. This stages calls for involvement of not only the victims, and service providers, but also the larger civil society, the policy makers, decision makers, the media and everyone who is

concerned with human rights. Every individual needs to realize that human trafficking affects everybody and anti trafficking should be considered as everybody's business.

Providing protection

Providing protection is not free from challenges. There is a lack of resources, lack of counseling services, marketing opportunities, lack of sustained interest among the agencies especially after the initial hype or a lack of reinforcing mechanisms. Sometimes acts of omission and commission which includes corruption, also add to the existing challenges (Nair, 2010).

Prosecution

Prosecution of offenders is fundamental in response to human trafficking. Human trafficking is an organized crime and there is no way to control and prevent this crime without prosecuting, convicting and punishing the persons involved in trafficking network. The concept of prosecution is not an easy task and it is multidimensional. It involves the register of crime in the police station, investigating the crime from an 'organized crime' perspective, prosecuting the offenders in the court of law by gathering evidence and ensuring that their conviction takes place. The job does not stop there, it includes confiscation of the assets, ensure that the offenders do not indulge in the similar crimes thereafter.

Prosecution thus involves in itself several activities and several stake holders are involved in the process. Investigators, forensic scientists, psycho-social counselors, lawyers, teachers, correctional service providers, executive magistrates, welfare officials, and judicial officers play important role in giving

relief to the victims. The importance of the prosecution can be best described by stating that it is the best available mechanism for controlling and preventing trafficking.

Indicators of Prosecution

In order to measure how effective the prosecution mechanism, it is important to look at the indicators of measurement. Within the Indian legal system the following indicators show effective prosecution-

Closure of the hotels or suspension of licences of hotels u/s -7 of ITPA.

Eviction of the offenders from the places of exploitation u/s 18 of the ITPA

Fine amount imposed on the offender by the respective authority under the laws of sexual exploitation and under labour exploitation.

Confiscation of the assets of the offenders

Release certificate issued by the SDM under the Bonded Labour Act

Compensation given to the victims by the government under the labour laws

Compensation paid by the offender to the victim, under the order of the court

Measures taken to exercise control on the advertisements which facilitate/ broadcast/ render exploitative labour or sexual orientation.

Justice Delivery

The police file charge sheet after investigating human trafficking crimes. Then judiciary plays a role in deciding the fate of the case. The ambience and environment in the court play in

deciding the victim's state of mind, the victim's deposition in the court of law. It is often suggested that the ambience in the court should be victim-friendly and it should be free from any unwanted disturbances. If necessary, the judicial officer should record evidence in his/her chamber. Procedures have been envisaged for in-camera trial u/s 327 Criminal Procedure Code. The court needs to provide for rest and recuperation of the victim and witness. The court also needs to consider the reimbursement of travel cost and contingencies that the victim/witness had to incur in attending to the court.

After ensuring that the court ambience is friendly, the court is also needed to pay attention to the court procedure. The court can consider providing a counselor to the victim, recording statement under 164 Criminal Procedure Code as and when required by a magistrate etc.

If needed, the court can also summon services of appropriate NGOs and ensure that they take care of the victim not only through counseling but also by providing support systems (Nair, 2010).

Prevention

Trafficking is a crime and it can be prevented. In fact, prevention is considered as the best mechanism to human trafficking. If the crime is completely prevented, then the question of rescue, investigation, prosecution, rehabilitation, restoration, court proceedings etc do not rise. But prevention is a complex process. It demands the arrest of the traffickers, conviction of the accused and the putting him behind the bars. Similarly, the victim is to be rehabilitated in true sense otherwise he/she can be very easily re-trafficked for sexual and labor exploitation. Re-trafficking is the bane of the

existing scenario of response. Many of the rescued victims are re-trafficked. Effective steps for protection and rehabilitation play a pivotal role in preventing of trafficking. Protection and prosecution also contribute significantly towards prevention. Ghosh and Kar (2006) state that community policing can be a very effective tool of combating the trafficking menace. The need to address the problem of sex trade simultaneously can be effective. Registration of the names of the domestic servants should be made compulsory to track their presence and the information to the Panchayat should also be made compulsory before leaving the village for job outside. The parents have a role to play in this respect. NGOs and the media should play a proactive role to support the victims who are courageous enough to report the case of trafficking (Ghosh and Kar, 2006). A sustain campaign is needed to make the poor and the vulnerable to become alert about the activities of the trafficking agents (Mukherjee, 2012).

Stake- Holders of Anti- Trafficking-

It is undeniable fact that the economic- and social globalization has brought the sea changes in the lives of the people. It has also gives birth to the unprecedented disparities among different sections of the society. It is often argued that this is the fallout of the human greed, lust and lasciviousness. Human trafficking, the gravest violations of the human rights, has also escalated in spite of the preventive mechanism in the world. It appears that the systems and the institutions have failed to deliver the desired results.

In the context of this dismal reality, the renewed efforts have been started to address the issue. Several stake- holders are involved in it and it is important to look at their role in the combat against human trafficking.

Police- Police is given power to attend all aspects of combating and preventing human trafficking. The police play the most crucial role in respect of this crime. They nab the traffickers and also rescue the victims. They conduct the investigation, try to ensure so that the victim is not victimized. They ensure the human rights, gender rights and by networking with NGOs and other Government departments, they try to rehabilitate and if needed, repatriate. They also make it sure that traffickers are prosecuted in the court of law.

Prosecutor

Prosecutor has to be sensitive while dealing the case of human trafficking. He should take proactive steps in the redressal of grievances. The prosecutor should bring to the notice of the court if the charge sheet has been filed by the police office against the victim of trafficking. Many times the accused persons adopt dilatory tactics by the accused and the prosecutor must bring that to the notice of the court and ensure remedial action. Prosecutor is expected to help police in getting statement u/s 164 of Criminal Procedure Code, recorded, in carrying out TIP (Test Identification Parade) and such other legal processes.

Judiciary

Delivery of justice and redressal of grievances lies with the judiciary. It fixes priority for trial and other issues in the justice delivery process, viz. TIP, disposing of bail matters etc. Judiciary can arrange in-camera trial proceedings whenever required and possible. It may also provide a safe ambience to the victim in the court by applying special provision. If the victim is traumatized, the judicial officer may record the statement in the chamber.

Medical Professionals

Role of medical professionals in Anti Human Trafficking seems to be secondary in nature. But the victim who is physically or sexually wounded looks forward to medical redressal as the first need. Medical professionals are called upon to perform a vast array of functions including age verification, expert opinion regarding the injury on the person etc.

Forensic Expert

Forensic Expert plays multifaceted role in Anti Human Trafficking. He is expected to act promptly on all requests as and when called for. Delay causes serious damage to the victim as well as the case. It is desirable that he should give opinion without delay. An expert may be called upon to conduct several tests on the body of the victim. The expert should keep in mind the dignity of the person and see that no further harm or damage happens.

Counsellors

The counselor should be a trained person and psycho- social expert. The counselor gives strength to the victim and witness. Counsellor can help the victim to discover oneself, reinvent oneself, and identify the work or field in which the victim can be empowered.

Counsellor should have right perspective and positive (Nair,2010).

Non Government Organizations-

There are multiple roles played by the NGOs in the field of anti human trafficking. NGOs are called upon to play roles like intelligence collection, conducting rescue, interviewing victim/ witnesses, counseling victims, providing

after care, rehabilitation, etc. They also work as the pressure group in making the responders respond appropriately etc. NGOs are also associated with providing training on anti trafficking.

Corporate/ Industrial Houses

Corporate and Industrial Houses with a corporate social responsibility (CSR) are important stake- holders in Anti Human Trafficking. Corporate can be a great source of empowerment to the rescued victims for extending all help, care and attention.

Teachers

Teachers have a crucial role to play in identifying patterns that lead to the human trafficking and they can play an important role in spreading awareness in the community.

Parents/ Guardians

They have the primary role to ensure that all the children are safe and secure. They need to remain alert and give information to their wards about the human trafficking.

Hotelier and Tourism Operators

In the context of commoditization of young children and growing sex tourism, the hoteliers and tourism operators need to remain cautious. They have to ensure that no individual is exploited for the sake of the business.

Researchers

Researchers also play a pivotal role by bringing the hard facts on the surface through research. Many misconceptions and myths have been busted by the research studies. The researchers bring the issues to the front which needs

immediate attention. Empirical research can bring out the issues in the objective way.

Labour Department Officials

The officials are expected to identify the places and areas where persons are engaged in exploitative labour or forced labour and they should take immediate action. There should not be any delay.

Labor Contractors

The labour contractors should ensure that no child is ever recruited or put for any labour.

Officials of Women and Child

Development Department

It is one of key departments which play a significant role in anti human trafficking initiatives. The department is expected to identify the vulnerability factors and should take necessary steps to reduce those. It works as the nodal agency in bringing about synergy of all stakeholders involved in the process.

District Magistrate/ Sub Divisional

Magistrate

Substantive laws and special laws have given the executive magistrates the power to take action to combat and prevent human trafficking. The Executive Magistrates (DM/SDM) can provide a host of services in this regard. They can, under the ITPA, direct rescue of a person who has been trafficked and any person who is likely to be trafficked.

Media

Media can play an effective role in anti human trafficking movement by spreading awareness among the masses.

Panchayati Raj Institutions

These grass root institutions can play an active role by identifying the vulnerable areas and vulnerable sections of population who are likely to be trafficked. Institutions can take remedial steps to reverse the situation.

Any Individual

Anti Human Trafficking is everybody's business. Anyone who is concerned about human rights can play a role in the combat against the trafficking. An individual can become a 'Whistle Blower' by bringing to the notice of the administration any incidence of trafficking. An individual can undertake public awareness campaign against human trafficking and empower the masses (Nair, 2010).

Political Leaders

Political Leaders can play an important role in the anti human trafficking movement. They are very good at bringing the stake holders of the movement together. They can easily identify the vulnerable people because of their connection with the grass root people and can ask the government officials to take prompt action to prevent the possible cases of trafficking. They can follow up the reported cases and by monitoring the cases initiate the rescue operation. They should also play a role so far reintegration is concerned of the rescued victims to the mainstream society.

Conclusion

Human trafficking is a serious crime. It is considered as the gross violation of the

human rights. Yet it is going on and most of the countries in the world are affected by this organized crime. The nation states have adopted different strategies to control it. But unfortunately, this illegal trade is generating huge illegal profits till date. It shows the ineffectiveness of the defense mechanism of the states. In most of the countries including India, provisions dealing with trafficking are designed to address 'prostitution' and not trafficking. One of the major constraints has been lack of validated data and information on trafficking. There is lack of researches because of the nature of the topic. In the recent period, researchers are taking interest on this issue and this would definitely contribute to build a good database which is primary need to formulate strategies to combat human trafficking.

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